

Updated dissemination and exploitation plan M36

SINTEF, Rita Ugarelli and Ida Rambæk

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ABSTRACT

The dissemination and exploitation plan summarizes the consortium's strategy and the concrete actions that should be made to disseminate and exploit the results generated by the project. This report defines and reports the dissemination and exploitation activities that have been and will be carried out during and after the project's life span. It contains the WIDER UPTAKE dissemination strategy, which is adopted to reach different types of audiences (stakeholders, general public, etc.), followed by a complete overview of the activity plan and the activities fulfilled. The wide range of dissemination activities has targeted and will target (until the end of the project) several types of communities, including water utilities, policy makers, researchers, and technology providers. The general public is also approached through the website, social media, Community of Practice and press coverage of the WIDER UPTAKE achievements and research results. The innovations of the project have been disseminated through several events, and efforts towards this goal are being made on a regular basis. The dissemination and use of the new developments will continue after the project's lifecycle, through the exploitation of research results and by pursuing possibilities of marketing via the established Water Europe Market Place. The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) was not a fixed document but evolved during the project's lifespan. This is the last version of the DEP, which finally evolved into its final form, i.e., this Deliverable 6.5 (due on M36). Nevertheless, the dissemination activities will continue until the end of the project and beyond.

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LEAD BENEFICIARY

SINTEF

AUTHOR(S)

Rita Ugarelli (SINTEF)

Ida Rambæk (SINTEF)

REVIEWED BY

Giorgio Mannina (UNIPA)

Herman Helness (SINTEF)

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1 Executive summary

The dissemination and exploitation plan (DEP) describes measures for the dissemination and exploitation of WIDER UPTAKE's results, and KPIs for measuring the effectiveness of the activities planned and performed.

WIDER UPTAKE aims to have an impact in the water and wastewater sector. The expected impact will rely on new industrial symbioses based on water-smart solutions that will link water and wastewater treatment, resource extraction, energy supply and product development for the agriculture, building & manufacturing materials industries, and energy supply. The results of WIDER UPTAKE will provide measures to overcome the existing barriers (social, economic, political) hampering the application of circular economy concepts to the water and wastewater sector. Five demonstration cases demonstrate explicitly how it is possible to achieve the recovery of resources from water and wastewater in symbiotic circular economy solutions provided by utilities and industries.

This document defines the key dissemination objectives of WIDER UPTAKE and details the steps that were taken up to M36 to achieve maximum impact and reach relevant audiences. It contains the WIDER UPTAKE dissemination strategy, which is adopted to reach different types of audiences (stakeholders, general public, etc.), followed by a complete overview of the activity plan. It also reports the dissemination activities that have been and will be carried out during and after the WIDER UPTAKE project's life span.

The DEP evolved during the lifespan of the project and formed the current report, i.e., Deliverable 6.5. In the current version, which is the third and last one, major updates are related to:

- Updating the dissemination activities that have been carried out in the first 36 months of the project for each dissemination and communication channel, i.e., the website, social media, newsletters/press releases/magazine, publications (in journals and conferences) and CoP events.
- Describing the upgrade of the official WIDER UPTAKE webpage.
- Reporting on the actions towards the insertion of "The WIDER UPTAKE case studies" under the existing Water Europe Market Place.
- Elaborating on the participation in EU and international events by WIDER UPTAKE Partners.
- Providing information on the clustering activities and networks that WIDER UPTAKE participates in.
- Updating on the exploitation activities fulfilled and planned for the following period.

Despite that D6.5 is due on M36, the dissemination and use of the new developments will continue until the end of the project and after its lifecycle, through the exploitation of research results and by pursuing marketing possibilities via the Water Europe Market Place.

2 Introduction

This document is developed as part of the WIDER UPTAKE project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, under the Grant Agreement number 869283.

The key to the success of WIDER UPTAKE is that generated knowledge is:

1. Efficiently exchanged among the consortium members to leverage the capability of each member, and
2. Successfully transferred to water utilities and external end-users and stakeholders, to better understand options, scenarios, opportunities, and challenges in the successful development and implementation of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) as a mean to increase resource efficiency.

This document summarises the plans and strategies within WIDER UPTAKE to fulfil these objectives. It additionally reports the activities implemented during the first 36 months of the project.

The second update (at M18) of the DEP, aimed to fine-tune, where needed, the defined strategy of appropriately planning and organizing all dissemination, exploitation as well as communication activities, and report on activities undertaken by the consortium for the promotion and diffusion of the results and findings to target audiences (scientific and educational community, general public, and stakeholders within the entire value chain). Further, within the second version of the DEP, a completely new section 4, focused on the tools and channels with related KPIs and targets, was added, while the original section 4 was split in sections from 5 to 10 elaborating with more details on each topic.

For the third and final version of the document which forms D6.5, the structure of the document remains the same. However, updates have been provided for dissemination activities that have been carried out in the first 36 months of the project for each dissemination channel, i.e., the website, social media, newsletters/ press releases/ magazine, publications (in journals and conferences) and Community of Practice (CoP) events, as well as the exploitation activities. Significant additions to this version of the DEP are the upgrade of the WIDER UPTAKE webpage as well as the actions performed to join the Water Europe Market Place as the chosen arena to maximize the project's exploitation opportunities.

The DEP of WIDER UPTAKE is outlined in the following sections:

- Section 1: Executive summary
- Section 2: Introduction
- Section 3: Outcomes of WIDER UPTAKE
- Section 4: Dissemination and exploitation of results
- Section 5: Open access and data management
- Section 6: Involvement of potential end-users and stakeholders
- Section 7: barriers to the implementation of results from WIDER UPTAKE
- Section 8: Implementation of results beyond project completion
- Section 9: Education of young professionals and researchers
- Section 10: Monitoring and evaluation of activities

2.1 About the project and its objectives

WIDER UPTAKE main goal is to facilitate industrial symbiosis as a mean to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. The project's hypothesis is that the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social, and economic character.

WIDER UPTAKE will identify and demonstrate common measures to overcome barriers related to:

1. 'Monitoring and control of health and quality risks'
2. 'Circular-economy (CE) and efficiency potential'
3. 'Governance and business models for industrial symbiosis'
4. 'Measuring water smartness and progress towards SDG'.

The project includes demonstrations at five different locations/countries/settings of:

- Wastewater reuse for agriculture and urban greening
- Phosphorus recycling, biogas, and biochar utilisation
- Production of bio composites for manufacturing materials with resources recovered from the whole water cycle.

The partnership in WIDER UPTAKE includes 11 water utilities and industries and 7 research institutes or universities, distributed across 5 countries (Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy, and Ghana).

The WIDER UPTAKE project aims to have an impact in the water sector. The expected impact will rely on water-smart symbiotic circular economy solutions that will link water and wastewater treatment, resource extraction, energy supply and product development for the agriculture, building & manufacturing materials industries, and energy supply. It is expected that the results of WIDER UPTAKE will provide measures to overcome the existing barriers (social, economic, political) hampering the application of circular economy concepts with such solutions in the water sector.

2.2 Objective of the exploitation and dissemination activities

According to the grant agreement, the exploitation and dissemination plan objective is to support the local partners in case-specific activities, to support companies in further development of symbiotic CE solutions, and to ensure knowledge transfer and uptake of WIDER UPTAKE main outcomes among citizens, utilities, policymakers, and the scientific community. More specifically, the objectives of exploitation activities are to i) Promote novel industrial symbiosis among the involved industrial stakeholders; ii) Promote the future creation of new companies/industrial activity focused on the CE and smart cities concept. Dissemination aims at maximising the impact of research results in the public domain.

Looking at the WP6 specific objectives:

- SO6.1: to develop and implement a roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions,
- SO6.2: to develop measures for exploitation of project results after the project period has ended,
- SO6.3: to promote a new market based on the water-smart system vision

- SO6.4: to disseminate the knowledge acquired

This deliverable represents the established plan to achieve the objectives SO6.2 and SO6.4.

3 Outcome of WIDER UPTAKE

3.1 Results

The WIDER UPTAKE project will have two types of results: i. direct results; ii. indirect results.

Direct results are expected to be:

- The improved understanding in terms of processes operation acquired by means laboratory and on-site (within the real plants) experimental tests.
- Mathematical models able to describe each part of the plants under study and to support their optimal operation in view of reducing the energy and resources employment according to a CE concept.
- Publications which summarize the results of the project published in the most relevant international journals that will be made available to the scientific community.
- Creation of a new market between Ghana and Sicily where products or sub-products of the project will be shared.
- A roadmap towards a water-smart society and related manual that includes all the mathematical models, set-up and calibrated, and all the knowledge acquired (social, economic, technical, and experimental) during the project.
- A framework for monitoring and controlling health and quality risks that can account for the multi-actor contributions to the risks in symbiotic relations between water utilities and industries in a circular economy context.
- A framework for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment and Optimisation of Symbiotic Solutions
- A tool for Governance assessment for circular economy based on water resources.
- A framework for holistic assessment of water smartness and progress towards SDGs
- A set of policy briefs enhancing the barriers to overcome.

Indirect results are expected to be:

- Materials (nutrients) recovery, sludge, and water reuse from wastewater treatment plants.
- Reduced energy usage from wastewater treatment plants.
- Reduction of biosolids production in wastewater treatment plants.
- Improvement of the stakeholders' awareness of the economic, environmental, and social convenience commercializing the products of the project (such as materials).

3.2 Innovations

The innovations in WIDER UPTAKE can be grouped in two groups. The first is existing innovations that already have been, and are developed, by the industry and partly utility partners in the case studies, e.g., bio composite material, 3D printed raingarden boxes, novel biofilm process for EBPR, novel adsorbents for nutrient recovery, biochar fuel products to replace charcoal or wood as fuel. These innovations are at different levels of maturity and the further development of the innovations themselves and the business plans, IPR-

management and other measures required for exploitation will be performed by the industry partners of the Consortium, e.g., Hias How20, HØST, NPSP, Storm Aqua, etc. in collaboration with the utilities.

These exploitation measures will be supported by WIDER UPTAKE activities but are not solely dependent on the project as such because the companies and utilities would anyhow be developing these measures as part of their already defined business model. The support activities in WIDER UPTAKE in Task 6.2.1 will be organised as part of the Communities of Practice (CoP). Business model development will be addressed specifically through WP4, task T4.2.2, which will explore innovative CE business models and test their applicability in the different demonstration cases. The aim is to facilitate further development of symbiotic solutions and to co-develop strategies for widespread implementation of these, thereby furthering market uptake of the technical innovations. WP6 will make the outcomes of the project visible and promote wider uptake through the Water Europe Market Place. As in any other marketplace, this is a place where demand meets (and matches) supply by giving access to products and services that come along with their characteristics, powerful capabilities and constraints and by providing a “digital” market for the three key players in the CE to interact: the problem owners – seeking to find the best solutions, the solutions providers – adding a technology or a product to the CE portfolio, and the investors – seeking opportunities to maximize investment revenues.

The other group of innovations in WIDER UPTAKE are the tools related to the methodologies for overcoming the barriers for wider uptake of water-smart solutions that are developed in the project. Exploitation of these tools in the project will be done as part of the activities in the respective WPs for the tools and in the case studies. These tools will have open access and the measures to secure exploitation of these will therefore be focused on informing the various potential users about the tools and providing means of access to the tools that will be effective also after the end of the project (e.g., via the Water Europe Market Place) The exploitation and dissemination plan of WIDER UPTAKE reflects the characteristics of the two groups of innovations and is focused on supporting the sharing of non-proprietary information – in the consortium and externally – and disseminating the results to a wide group of recipients.

4 Dissemination and exploitation of results

4.1 Dissemination and Exploitation strategic principles

The following set of strategic cross-cutting principles will underpin the dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts:

1. **Focus on the solutions rather than on “the project”.** The end goal of WIDER UPTAKE is to demonstrate innovative solutions for wastewater reuse and resource recovery where market utilisation of the recovered resource(s) (water, nutrients, materials, energy) is achieved through a symbiosis between the utility and industry. The exploitation and dissemination activities will reflect the commercial and business nature of these solutions in circular water management. This is now most tangible in the revised design of the project website which has been tuned more towards the solutions than the project (see section 4.4.2).
2. **Stories** will be key in making the benefits of the solutions tangible to their target audience. The dissemination will focus on highlighting the positive aspects (services, benefits; added value to companies/citizens) instead of the more ‘negative’ ones

(threats from climate change, for example) through storylines that resonate with daily lives and working processes. Factsheets describing the case studies in this sense have already been produced as collaboration of the CIRSEAU cluster (see sections 4.4.4 and 4.4.8).

3. **Establish a recognizable and attractive brand identity.** A recognisable visual identity and the brand have been developed for WIDER UPTAKE, ensuring its suitability for both the project and commercial phases (see section 4.4.1).
4. **Focus communication towards specific, targeted audiences.** Instead of large-scale communication, the focus will be set on reaching out to particular actors. The utilities and technology providers will be interviewed to test the unique selling propositions and narratives. While tailoring the dissemination plan for each story, WP6 will still ensure that the results are brought together coherently to enable their exportation to areas outside their case studies through the Water Europe Market Place (see section 8).
5. **Leverage multipliers to maximise impacts.** Networks, organisations, relevant individuals, or media have the potential to significantly boost the project dissemination and communication efforts. A success story in this regard is the establishment of the network CIRSEAU composed of the four projects funded under the same call as WIDER UPTAKE; the five projects, under the guidance of EC, have actively collaborated by starting a process of systematically mapping commonalities in terms of topics, case studies, technologies, methodological frameworks, target regions, and stakeholders (see section 4.4.8).

4.2 Target groups

Carefully defining the target audiences is the key to getting the messages across. There are five target groups for WIDER UPTAKE (in alignment with the Communication plan, D7.4):

- Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers,
- Stakeholders (e.g., business organisations, city networks and association, etc.),
- Scientific community,
- European and national policy makers,
- Citizens.

This section describes these target groups in more detail, outlining communication objectives, narratives, and key messages for each. The initial set of key messages has been defined during the update of this plan in M18 of the project and it has been further refined in this update of M36. In M36 these messages have been complemented by specific value propositions, targeted at exploitation and market uptake of the solutions, and defined in collaboration with WP4, which will develop the circular economy synergies business models. For further details we refer to the deliverable D4.2: Business models and strategies for industrial symbiosis based on water-smart solutions (M36).

4.2.1 Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers

Water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers are the direct beneficiaries and potential users of most of the WIDER UPTAKE solutions. The specific communication objective in relation to this group is market uptake, replication of the technologies as well as capacity building and raising awareness about the solutions demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE.

Communication aimed at water managers has made and will make use of specific channels and means to convey the project progress:

- CoP session of collaborative work
- The Water Europe Market place
- Organisation of public local events at the case studies locations
- Dedicated features in the project newsletter
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions

WIDER UPTAKE is about to join the Water Europe Marketplace (see Section 8) and a number of CoP meetings were already held in the case studies as reported in D7.6: 1. Report on Communities of Practice (M18, which will be updated with a second CoP- report (D7.8) in M44.

Public local events were organized by the Partners as reported in periodic technical report, Part A.

A preliminary identification of international and national trade fairs and exhibitions is available in Table 3, while **Error! Reference source not found.** depicts the events attended by WIDER UPTAKE.

4.2.2 Local stakeholders

The stakeholders' category includes regional/local authorities, private companies, end users, business organisations, city networks and association, etc. Task 4.2 has already identified a list of local stakeholders per demo site which will be addressed.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is to raise awareness about WIDER UPTAKE and engage for further dissemination and co-development of the solutions. The CoP (Task 7.3) has been the crucial channel to reach this target audience (D7.6 and D7.8). Some snapshots of the events reported by Task 7.3 are given in the pictures below (Figures 1 to 7).

Figure 1 Stakeholder workshop in Accra, February 2023

Figure 2 Stakeholder workshop in Delft, December 2022

Figure 3 Wider Uptake partners and stakeholders met in a “mobile lab” in Palermo, October 2022

Figure 4 Stakeholders engagement at the Czech demo cases – June 2022.

Figure 5 Consortium meeting in Hamar, June 2022

Figure 6 Stakeholders meeting in Prague, June 2021

4.2.3 Scientific community

The third audience is the scientific community who will use the information and results to exchange on urban water management challenges, building on the WIDER UPTAKE findings and results. Figure 7 illustrates some dissemination efforts among the scientific community. This scientific community refers to the research community working in the field of treatment/processing technologies, circular economy in the water sector and water and energy management.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is exploitation of results in further scientific discussions and research. This has been, is and will be performed through the collaboration with the established networks (e.g., CIRSEAU), publications in relevant Journals (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) as well as by participating to conferences and events targeting the research community (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Zoran Kapelan presented water smartness in Naples

The keynote talk questioned what is a smart solution in the water sector.

[Read more](#)

Jiří Wanner presented WIDER UPTAKE

The town of Tabor hosted the 24th Czech national conference on "New Trends in Wastewater treatment and Water Supply".

[Read more](#)

Wider Uptake in South Korea

From 23 to 26 November, Giorgio Mannina, professor of sanitary-environmental engineering at the University of Palermo, and researcher in Wider Uptake, was invited to participate in the 8th International Water [...]

[Read more](#)

Prize for best presentation to Adéla Puškačková

Adéla Puškačková received the prize for the presentation "Nanofiltration for treatment of effluent from municipal wastewater treatment plant for the purpose of its recycling".

[Read more](#)

Figure 7 Some examples of Partner's dissemination efforts in the scientific community ([News and events – Wider Uptake \(wider-uptake.eu\)](#))

4.2.4 European and National policymakers

The fourth target audience are the European and National policymakers. The WIDER UPTAKE results will lead to the formulation of policy recommendations that will be disseminated towards the policy audience who will make decisions on the enabling policy frameworks. More precisely, they refer to:

- National Ministries/Departments of Environment/Science & Technology
- European Commission DG DIGIT, ENV, REGIO, AGRI, GROW
- MEP Water Group, Water JPI
- European level associations such as Water Europe, EIP Water, EIP Agri.

The **specific communication objective** in relation to this group is the implementation of the WIDER UPTAKE policy recommendations for short to medium-term policy developments in the EU and case study countries.

At the time of writing, the project has created one policy brief (Figure 8): WIDER UPTAKE Policy brief #1: [BROADENING THE SCOPE IN WATER MANAGEMENT](#). It has been disseminated via the project webpage and LinkedIn account. Further it has been distributed to the project partners and been used as basis for communication with stakeholders, e.g., in a Norwegian water sector meeting organised to discuss solutions to wastewater and sludge management in Oslo, April 2023 (Figure 9).

Figure 8 The first Policy brief of WIDER UPTAKE disseminated through the website and the project's LinkedIn -page

WIDER UPTAKE – sirkulær økonomi i vannbransjen

Figure 9 From presentation (in Norwegian) at Norwegian water sector meeting organised to discuss solutions to wastewater and sludge management in Oslo, April 2023

4.2.5 Citizens

The last category is citizens who will directly benefit from the environmental and societal benefits brought by the WIDER UPTAKE solutions.

The **specific communication objectives** about this group are to make the public aware about urban water issues, to foster the public use and social acceptance of circularities enabled by WIDER UPTAKE.

The WIDER UPTAKE case study owners have given relevant attention to the communication towards citizens' engagement, citizens awareness and acceptance through the dedicated local events (examples of events are presented in the following pictures: Figures 10 to 13).

Figure 10 Prof Giorgio Mannina presenting the activities at the University of Palermo, on Italian national television – TGI - <https://www.facebook.com/WiderUptakeUnipa/videos/1308503529886554>

Figure 11 Wider - Uptake project at SHARPER (SHaring Researchers' Passions for Evidences and Resilience) 2022 - [European Researcher's Night](#).

Mezinárodní projekt Wider Uptake

Figure 12 [Prof. Jaroslav Pollert from the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the Czech Technical University in Prague presenting WIDER UPTAKE in a interview meant for students and citizens audience.](#)

Figure 13 [Dissemination on TV Prague](#)

4.3 Dissemination and exploitation content

The content has evolved with the progress of the project. In the beginning, the content has been primarily focused on the expected benefits of each solution. The focus has increasingly shifted to the concrete outcomes of each solution and their market uptake.

4.3.1 Dissemination content per WP

The dissemination actions reflect the strategic milestones of the project, and the aim is to ensure that all relevant outcomes resulting from the different WPs are communicated.

While the information is communicated widely, the messages are tailored to fit the characteristics and needs of each audience and channel in order to reach audience in the most relevant way.

For instance, the following popular science articles have been published from the different work packages:

WP 1 and 2:

<https://norwegianscitechnews.com/2022/10/it-is-not-enough-to-save-water-we-must-also-reuse-it/>

WP 1 and 3:

<https://norwegianscitechnews.com/2022/03/recovering-eco-friendly-phosphorous-from-wastewater/>

WP 1 and 5:

<https://norwegianscitechnews.com/2021/02/effective-fertiliser-from-wastewater-phosphorous/>

4.3.2 Dissemination content per solution and outcomes

The solutions are at the heart of the project. Therefore, developing specific messages (examples shown in Figure 14), value propositions and stories linked to the motivations of those who use these solutions is also important also in view of further exploitation.

While the messages to be communicated evolves with the project's progress, a first set of messages/storylines will be developed. WP6, Task 6.2.1 will coordinate the process with each solution developer during the last year of the project, in a strategy aligned with the business model development in WP4 and in parallel with further development of the website content.

Hamar workshop – April 2022

The workshop was hosted by Hias at the new water treatment facility, and all the participants got to see the ongoing activity for implementing the Hias process and the new struvite plant.

[Read more](#)

Installation of biochar production line at SSGL – Accra

Installation of biochar production line at SSGL – Accra The Mudor Treatment Plant treats wastewater from Accra, the capital of Ghana, and has a capacity of 18 000 m3/day. Biochar [...]

[Read more](#)

Wastewater fertilisers to the aid of farmers

Municipal wastewater treatment plants are now planning to recover more of these valuable resources, which are becoming globally scarce.

[Read more](#)

Reuse of wastewater in urban agriculture – Accra

Despite the increasing urbanisation, there has not been a national discourse on water-smart solutions for the nation nor for urban areas that face perennial water shortages.

[Read more](#)

Figure 14 Examples of solutions dedicated dissemination ([News and events – Page 2 – Wider Uptake \(wider-uptake.eu\)](#))

4.4 Tools and channels

4.4.1 Logo and visual identity

In order to maintain a cohesive image and make the project and its outputs readily identifiable, a project logo and a corporate design has been created by the partner SINTEF, (Figure 15). This logo is displayed in all project materials, such as website, social media profiles, leaflets, conference presentations, publications, videos, etc.

Figure 15 WIDER UPTAKE logo

Concomitantly, templates for Word documents, PowerPoint presentations and publications (such as reports) were made available for partners.

According to the Grant Agreement and general EU research funding rules, any dissemination of results must acknowledge EU Horizon 2020 funding, by displaying the EU emblem, with appropriate prominence, and including the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869283”.

Also, any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. It is recommended to display the following text in any report or another kind of publication:

“The publication reflects only the authors’ views, and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”

For presentations the following text should be used in the same manner:

“This presentation reflects only the authors’ views, and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.”

4.4.2 Website

The public project website is available since Month 3 at: <https://www.wider-uptake.eu> and has been revised after the project review in February 2022 to focus on results, deliverables, and activities in the demo cases, while still providing information about the project, objectives, and the consortium (Figure 16).

A new web page with a new menu structure, highlighting the solutions and products developed in the demo cases, was published in 2022 (Figure 17). The new menu structure presents the content in a more user-oriented way and focuses less on the organisation of the project.

A pop-up-function for Newsletter subscription was also added. Here visitors can subscribe for the newsletter via a pop-up message inviting to register.

The webpage is continuously updated with results and project news (in blog format). The website allows to promote, among other things, project materials, press releases, publications, project results for download, as well as links to social media channels. Links to partner websites and relevant organizations are featured.

Figure 16 – WIDER UPTAKE website, before M18

Wider uptake of watersmart solutions

WIDER UPTAKE is an EU-project that brings together researchers, water utilities and private industries in five countries. The aim is to find the best possible use of water resources, reduce carbon emissions and develop sustainable business models.

To ensure clean water, food and good living conditions for all, we must utilize more of the resources in water. And it is not necessarily a question of technology, today the barriers are just as often regulations and lack of business models.

WIDER UPTAKE demonstrates innovative solutions that optimize water reuse, resource recovery and energy utilisation. Market utilisation of the recovered resources is achieved through a symbiosis between the utility and industry

[Learn more](#)

Solutions and Products

Reuse of waste water in urban

Greening of urban areas with

New bio-composite material from

Figure 17 Updated WIDER UPTAKE website, after M18

Local websites in local languages have also been created, with specific information about the local demonstration cases and country specific information, see the following link of local websites:

Italian: <https://wideruptake.unipa.it/home>

Prague: <https://wider-uptake.webnode.cz/>

4.4.3 Social media

A Facebook and a LinkedIn account were established from March 2021

- <https://www.facebook.com/groups/489234269105783/about/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wider-uptake>

The social media accounts have been regularly updated with news items from the project. UNIPA has also created accounts for the project on Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter:

<https://m.facebook.com/WiderUptakeUnipa/>

<https://twitter.com/WiderUptake>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/wideruptake-unipa/>

At the time of writing, the UNIPA project profile on Twitter has 431 followers and the project page on LinkedIn 154 followers, while the Facebook group has 22 members and will probably not be maintained to focus on further increasing the impact via Twitter and LinkedIn. The two platforms are considered sufficient to the scope. Twitter is widely used in B2B and B2C communications and allows to reach a large number of people. Experience from previous related projects indicate that many relevant players for WIDER UPTAKE can be reached via Twitter. LinkedIn is particularly appropriate when it comes to reaching leaders in state and private organisations. Thus, this is an appropriate digital tool for water/wastewater utilities and city decision-makers or more broadly, stakeholders. In a nutshell, LinkedIn gives the possibility for employees and employers to create profiles and “connections” to each other that are professionally related.

The hashtag #wideruptake has also been used by project partners to amplify the dissemination of news and updates from the project. We also encourage all partners to tag the project page when posting relevant updates on LinkedIn.

In terms of social media traffic, Figure 18 provides an overview of the impressions experienced in LinkedIn in the period 2022-March 2023 - while Figure 19 provides an overview of the follower analytics in LinkedIn and Figure 20 depicts, just for illustration purposes, the best performing posts on LinkedIn in 2022.

Figure 18 Overview of the impressions experienced in LinkedIn in the period 2022-March 2023

Follower demographics

Location ▾

Show all →

Follower demographics

Job function ▾

Figure 19 Follower analytics from LinkedIn

Figure 20 Best performing posts on LinkedIn in 2022

Furthermore, the results from Wider Uptake are also shared in the partners web pages and social media channels, which reach a much broader national and international audience than the project channels. E.g., SINTEF Community page on LinkedIn with 14.363 followers:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/9403662/admin/>

4.4.4 Information materials

WP7, Task 7.4, will make available information material such as brochures and factsheets made available in the project website in printable version, so to be downloaded and handout by Partners during events on need.

4.4.4.1 Press Releases & News Stories

Press releases and stories from the project have so far been distributed in the Norwegian *SciTech* news and made available on the [project website](#) (Figure 21).

The press releases are targeting a broad audience and the focus is on the social and economic benefits of reusing resources in wastewater. The three press releases so far produced describe the benefits of the solutions developed in the Demo Cases in Norway, Ghana, and the Czech Republic. They have reached a broad audience in Norway and in international science press.

Figure 21 Screenshots of the Press releases and stories from the project posted in [Press Releases and Articles – Wider Uptake \(wider-uptake.eu\)](#)

4.4.4.2 Newsletter

To spread information about the project’s progress and developments, news published on the project web site are distributed in a newsletter twice a year. The newsletter has 126 subscribers (March 2023), and new subscribers can register directly on the web page.

The newsletter highlights results and deliverables, such as the first Policy brief from the project. Recent activities and events are also included. Screenshot of newsletter from December 2022 is inserted below (Figure 22):

Figure 22 Screenshots of the WIDER UPTAKE Newsletters

4.4.4.3 POWER POINT PRESENTATION OF THE PROJECT

A general project presentation has been created to support the dissemination by the Partners (Figure 23). It gives an overview of the mission, impact and the products and solutions that are being developed within the project: <https://wider-uptake.eu/objectives>

Wider Uptake of Water-smart Solutions

MISSION: WIDER UPTAKE aims to facilitate industrial symbiosis in order to increase resource efficiency, limit emissions and develop sustainable business based on water-smart solutions. Our hypothesis is that the barriers are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social and economic character.

IMPACT: After demonstrating water-smart, circular economy solutions, we will develop an open access roadmap on how to upscale and implement such solutions on a wider scale, in Europe and beyond.

Partners

- **11 Water Utilities and Industries:** SSGL, AMAP S.p.A., PVS, Storm Aqua, WATNL, NPSP BV, Hias IKS, HIAS How2O AS, Sirkula, IVAR IKS and Terramarine
- **7 Research Institutions:** SINTEF, NTNU, TU Delft, CVUT, VSCHT, UNIPA, CSIR-GH
- **5 Countries:** Norway, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Italy, Ghana

Figure 23 Screenshot of the general presentation of the project

4.4.5 Publications

The ambition of the WIDER UPTAKE team is to prepare and submit at least 15 articles to scientific journals open access (gold option); the publications will cover specific results at demo case level, as well as the horizontal topics of WIDER UPTAKE, such as the smartness-assessment framework and the risk assessment approach.

In WIDER UPTAKE, the most suitable journals for each content should be selected based on the following criteria:

- Open access options
- Scientific impact
- Disciplinary and methodological fit

A tentative list of scientific journals to which WIDER UPTAKE articles may be submitted is provided in Table 1. Due to the timings of peer-review and scientific publication, we expect to have 20 articles submitted by the end of the project. As of M36, 10 journal papers have been published. The remaining are expected to be under review at the of the project period, with publication dates in the following two or three years. The WIDER UPTAKE team will also seek to publish other kinds of scientific publications, such as book chapters and edited issues of journals or monographies whenever possible.

In addition to the above activities, WIDER UPTAKE has published a book by Elsevier publishing. The title is "Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering - Smart Solutions for Wastewater: Road-mapping the Transition to Circular Economy". The intention of this publication is to provide students and professionals with a knowledge base around the topics covered in WIDER UPTAKE. Access to this knowledge base can represent an inspiration for practitioners, students, and young professionals to actively contribute to the transition to a circular economy with water smart solutions ([Current Developments in Biotechnology and Bioengineering - 1st Edition \(elsevier.com\)](https://www.elsevier.com/locate/S0167636920300000)). A second book with working

title: *Boosting the transition to circular economy in the water sector: insights from EU demonstration case studies* is planned for publication in 2024.

Table 1: Preliminary identification of Scientific Journals

EU/ international	Bioresource Technology Environment Technology Environmental Challenges Environmental Engineering and Management Journal Environmental Management Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts European Journal of Sustainable Development International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health International Journal of Water Resources Development IWA Publishing AQUA IWA Publishing Blue-Green Systems IWA Publishing H2 Open Journal IWA Publishing Water & Health IWA Publishing Water Policy IWA Publishing Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing Water Quality Research Journal IWA Publishing Water Reuse Journal IWA Publishing Water Science & Technology IWA Publishing Water Supply IWA Publishing Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development Journal of Environmental Management Journal of Environmental Psychology Land Use and Planning Local Environment Membranes (MDPI) Microorganism (MDPI) Procedia Engineering Research Involvement and Engagement Resources, Conservation & Recycling Science Communication Science of the Total Environment Separation & Purification Technology Strategic Management Journal Sustainability (MDPI) Urban Water Journal Water (MDPI) Water Research Water Resources Management Water Reuse & Desalination
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Furthermore, WIDER UPTAKE will make use of the new open access publication outlet of the European Commission: [Open Research Europe](#). This is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding across all subject areas. This will allow us to comply with the open access terms of the funding and seems to be a promising venue to share results and insights swiftly and to facilitate open, constructive research discussion.

Regarding the research data generated by the research activities, the partners will deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the data. This includes associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible, and other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan'. They will also

provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the partners and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves). The management of these data will be made in accordance with the Project's DMP and in compliance with the EU Intellectual Property Rights Regulations.

This is done strictly in conformity with the obligations of maintaining anonymity, confidentiality, security and protecting personal data. Data archiving makes use of the services provided by OpenAire (www.openaire.eu) and ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>) where the WIDER UPTAKE has established a dedicated repository.

The WIDER UPTAKE publications (Table 2) are available on the project's website under Results / Publications (<https://wider-uptake.eu/publications>) and in the WIDER UPTAKE Open Access repository on Zenodo (Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions | Zenodo).

Table 2: WIDER UPTAKE journal publications

Journal	Citation/Reference
Bioresource Technology	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.128217
Environmental Challenges	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100645
Bioresource Technology	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127951
Bioresource Technology	https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127929
Microorganism	https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10102073
Water Practice & Technology	https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2022.081
Bioresource Technology.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.125812
Bioresource Technology.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.125853
Water	https://doi.org/10.3390/w13070946
Science of the total Environment	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144026

4.4.6 Audio-visual marketing materials

By month 36, the project has produced eight videos of which four in the form of interviews to the partners (<https://youtu.be/H2pF9W2UnmE>, <https://youtu.be/7GFR1Riyiwg>; <https://youtu.be/OOSdVw41IKk>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0heVu-gkx7I>), one as animated video presenting the WIDER UPTAKE general concept (WIDER-UPTAKE.UNIPA) and one as presentation at the EWA Water Reuse Webinar, <https://youtu.be/01w7aAz99NM>. During next reporting period, the project will produce videos showcasing the success stories and the main results of the project. All videos can be reached at <https://wider-uptake.eu/videos>

4.4.7 Conferences and events

Due to the covid pandemic conferences and events during the first 18 months have been local/national events with participation of WIDER UPTAKE limited to the partners of the five demonstration cases. More active participation to events in person started when the pandemic situation allowed it. Table 3 provides a non-exhaustive list of events where participation from WIDER UPTAKE is planned.

Table 3: Events and conferences

Title of the event	City	Country	Date	Website
NORDIWA - Leading Nordic event for water professionals	Göteborg	Sweden	5-7/09/2023	https://www.nordiwa.org/
6th IWA International Conference on Eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment	Girona	Spain	26-29/06/2023	https://iwa-network.org/events/6th-iwa-international-conference-on-eco-technologies-for-wastewater-treatment/
Novatech International Conference on solutions and strategies for more sustainable urban water management	Lyon	France	03-07/07/2023	https://iwa-network.org/events/novatech-international-conference-on-solutions-and-strategies-for-more-sustainable-urban-water-management/
10th IWA Membrane Technology Conference & Exhibition for Water and Wastewater Treatment and Reuse	St. Louis, Missouri	USA	23-26/07/2023	https://iwa-network.org/events/the-10th-iwa-membrane-technology-conference-exhibition-for-water-and-wastewater-treatment-and-reuse/
IWA Sustainable Sludge Management 2024	Beijing	China	17-20/05/2024	https://iwa-network.org/events/iwa-conference-on-sustainable-sludge-management/
WIDER UPTAKE organised conference: International Conference on Wider-Uptake of Water Resource Recovery from wastewater treatment – ICWRR	Palermo	Italy	19-21/06/2024	

12 contributions (oral presentations with or without abstract or full paper, and posters with or without presentations) have so far been made, or will be, in conferences with acceptance of participation after peer review (Table 4). It is highlighted though, that the partners have also participated in several (34 from the start of the project until M36) other conferences with oral presentation or posters.

Table 4: WIDER UPTAKE presence in Events and conferences

Title of the event	Event website	Title of the contribution	Type of contribution (Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation/Poster)	Partner	Evidence if available
NORDIWA 2023 Nordic Wastewater Conference 5 - 7 September Göteborg Sweden	https://event.trippus.net/Home/Index/AEAKglMaG_e-V4r0oWSpOK-Bo3h67f75OaewQnTqMmF0CskEhjoKX77nb8Cw9ic_L_TzdmuEoGns/AEAKglNs556bTDAOFzV1YhDIEkrbvHdZFe8-IM0LLkyHI7iyJrdhk788ec1PvpTtYGw-F3gsdk1/eng	Risks assessment of PFAS in a biological phosphorus recovery sludge used for agriculture	Oral presentation	NTNU-SINTEF	
NORDIWA 2023 Nordic Wastewater Conference 5 - 7 September Göteborg Sweden	https://event.trippus.net/Home/Index/AEAKglMaG_e-V4r0oWSpOK-Bo3h67f75OaewQnTqMmF0CskEhjoKX77nb8Cw9ic_L_TzdmuEoGns/AEAKglNs556bTDAOFzV1YhDIEkrbvHdZFe8-IM0LLkyHI7iyJrdhk788ec1PvpTtYGw-F3gsdk1/eng	Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions – the H2020 project WIDER UPTAKE in a Nordic context	Oral presentation	SINTEF	
NORDIWA 2023 Nordic Wastewater Conference 5 - 7 September Göteborg Sweden	https://event.trippus.net/Home/Index/AEAKglMaG_e-V4r0oWSpOK-Bo3h67f75OaewQnTqMmF0CskEhjoKX77nb8Cw9ic_L_TzdmuEoGns/AEAKglNs556bTDAOFzV1YhDIEkrbvHdZFe8-IM0LLkyHI7iyJrdhk788ec1PvpTtYGw-F3gsdk1/eng	Water smartness and sustainability of symbiotic solutions for water reuse and resource recovery	Oral presentation	SINTEF	
10th International Water Association Membrane Technology Conference & Exhibition for Water and Wastewater Treatment and Reuse, July 23 – 26, 2023, Washington University in St. Louis, USA.	https://iwa-network.org/event/the-10th-iwa-membrane-technology-conference-exhibition-for-water-and-wastewater-treatment-and-reuse/	Effect of sludge recirculation ratio on the performance of an MBR-OSA system treating domestic wastewater	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications

10th International Water Association Membrane Technology Conference & Exhibition for Water and Wastewater Treatment and Reuse, July 23 – 26, 2023, Washington University in St. Louis, USA.	As above	Water Reuse from Wastewater Treatment by Conventional Activated Sludge and Ultrafiltration Membrane: Case Study of Corleone	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
10th International Water Association Membrane Technology Conference & Exhibition for Water and Wastewater Treatment and Reuse, July 23 – 26, 2023, Washington University in St. Louis, USA.	As above	VFA from sewage sludge by anaerobic membrane bioreactors: lesson learned from two-year experiments within Wider-Uptake EU project	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
EurEau Committee 1, 07.02.2023		Sustainable and Resource Efficient Water Supply – Circular Economy Solutions in Water Supply	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	TU Delft	
EU legislation for wastewater reuse, seminar CzWA, Prague, CZ, February 2023		REGULATION (EU) 2020/741 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
Demonstration pilot units of wastewater reuse for irrigation of urban greenery in Prague, February 2023		Wiederverwendung von gereinigtem Abwasser	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
The Norwegian Environmental Chemistry Symposium, January 29 - February 1, 2023, Geilo, Norway.	https://www.envirochem.no/	Risks assessment and distribution of PFAS in a biological phosphorus recovery sludge used for agriculture	Oral presentation at Conference	NTNU-SINTEF	https://portal.styrerweb.com/api/files/5148565/IVyCW6DAUkWGxGOKpxD_uQ/Programme_NECS2023_YTH_Final_230118.pdf?DocLinkId=19617&ref=%2ffinalprogramme%2f

17th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems, Paphos, Cyprus, November 2022		Reuse of treated wastewater in agricultural irrigation	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
24th Conference on New trends in wastewater treatment, Envipur Co. and CzWA, Tábor, CZ, November 2022		EU Guidelines to support the application of Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
11th IWA International Symposium of Waste Management Problems in Agro-Industry, Gdansk (Poland) 26-28 October 2022.	https://iwa-network.org/event/s/11th-iwa-international-symposium-on-waste-management-problems-in-agro-industries/	Sewage sludge minimization by using an OSA-MBR pilot plant	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
11th IWA International Symposium of Waste Management Problems in Agro-Industry, Gdansk (Poland) 26-28 October 2022.	https://iwa-network.org/event/s/11th-iwa-international-symposium-on-waste-management-problems-in-agro-industries/	Enhancing polyhydroxyalkanoates (bioplastic) production and recovery from wastewater	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
11th IWA International Symposium on Waste Management Problems in Agro-Industry, Gdansk (Poland) 26-28 October 2022.		Enhancing membrane bioreactor optimization for water reuse: A pilot-scale experimental study	Poster	UNIPA	
12th Conference of the Slovak Wastewater Association, Wastewater 2022, Štrbské Pleso, Slovakia, October 2022		Effect of wastewater irrigation on soil bacteria activity	Poster	VSCHT	
14th General Conference VODA 2021, Litomyšl (Czech Republic), 22-24 September 2022.		Reuse of treated wastewater from municipal WWTP for irrigation of urban greenery.	Poster	VSCHT	
IWA World Water Congress & Exhibition held 11-	https://iwa-network.org/event/s/iwa-world-water-congress-	A WWTP's transition towards circularity; a full-scale testimony on	Poster	HIAS	

15 September 2022	exhibition-2022-copenhagen/	the novel Hias-Process			
IWA World Water Congress & Exhibition held 11-15 September 2022	https://iwa-network.org/event/s/iwa-world-water-congress-exhibition-2022-copenhagen/	Harmonized monitoring framework for the evaluation of soil improver product from municipal wastewater: Regulations and risk assessment	Poster	NTNU-SINTEF	
Conference of YWP 2022, Brno, CZ, 6-7 September 2022		Nanofiltration for treatment of effluent from municipal wastewater treatment plant for the purpose of its recycling	Poster	VSCHT	
XL SICA Congress, 5-7 September 2022, Pisa, Italy.	https://sica2022.azuleon.org/mySICA	Zeolite–Ammonium interactions: the physical-chemistry of the adsorption process.	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
XL SICA Congress, 5-7 September 2022, Pisa, Italy.		Zeolite–Ammonium interactions: the physical-chemistry of the desorption process	Poster	UNIPA	
XL SICA Congress, 5-7 September 2022, Pisa, Italy.		Phosphorous recovery from treated wastewater by salt activated biochar	Poster	UNIPA	
PhD Course/Workshop 'Innovation and Sustainability Transitions', University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway, August 25, 2022		The WIDER UPTAKE Project: Ghana's Demonstration Case	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	CSIR	
5th Efficient Water Systems (EWaS) international conference, Naples, Italy, 12 July 2022		Smart Solutions for Secure and Sustainable Urban Water Management	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	TU Delft	
iEMSs 2022 Conference, Belgium 4-7 July 2022	https://www.iems2022.com/	Resources Recovery from Wastewater Treatment Plants: Full Scale Optimization by Using a Mathematical	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications

		Model Including Greenhouse Gas Emissions			
International Conference on Water, Waste and Energy Management, 2 June 2022	https://waset.org/water-waste-and-energy-management-conference-in-june-2022-in-san-francisco	A Dynamic Model for Circularity Assessment of Nutrient Recovery from Domestic Sewage	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	TU Delft	
European Water Association Water Symposium, June 2022		Source Control Strategy for Micro Pollutants	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	VSCHT	
European Water Association Pre-IFAT workshop, May 2022		Wastewater reuse in the European Union and in the Czech Republic	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
Czech – Israeli Seminar on Potential benefits and dilemmas in the development of a national viruses control system via sewage technologies for treatment of drinking water and waste water (technologies that are developed and used in Israel), 25-26 April 2022		Disinfection of municipal effluents by using UV light and peroxy acids: Experience from Horizon 2020 project “Achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions”	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	VSCHT	
Wastewater, Water and Resource Recovery Conference 2022, 10-13 April 2022		Qualitative risk assessment for bio-composite materials production	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	TU Delft	
New legal norms in sector "Water" of the European Union, March 2022		Nové metody a postupy při provozování ČOV	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
Energie- en Grondstoffenfabriek (Energy and Resources Factory) - Workgroup Clippings, 15 December 2021		Bio-composites of residual flows from the water cycle and from the water board	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	NPSP	
Time for Sustainability - Delfland Water Board, 15 December 2021		Bio-composites of residual flows from the water cycle and from the water board	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	NPSP	
24th Conference on New trends in wastewater treatment, Envipur Co. and CzWA,		WWTPs as sources of water for the future: project EU Horizon 2020 - irrigation of urban greenery using	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	

Tábor, CZ, 9 November 2021		effluent from CWWTP Prague			
4th IWA Resource Recovery Conference, Turkey 5-8 September 2021.	https://watermining.eu/4th-iwa-resource-recovery-conference-2021-5-8-september-2021-istanbul-turkey/	Volatile fatty acids from urban wastewater and sewage sludge: batch test experiments.	Peer reviewed paper/oral presentation	UNIPA	https://wideruptake.unipa.it/publications
XII International Conference "Chemistry and Chemical Engineering in XXI Century", Tomsk (Russia), 17-20 March 2021		Wastewater reuse for irrigation of municipal greens (2021).	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
Water Biology, Prague (Czech Republic). (In Czech), 10-11 February 2021		Recycling of runoff from a municipal WWTP and possibilities of its disinfection.	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	VSCHT	
The 14th IHE PhD Symposium 2020, 8 October 2020		Assessment and management of health and quality risk for (waste)water reuse and resource recovery	Presentation at Conference/Workshop	TU Delft	

4.4.8 Multipliers & synergies

Connections with other similar projects will be actively sought. The WIDER UPTAKE team has assessed which H2020 projects, especially in the same and related calls, have commonalities in market domain and technical implementation with the scope of mutual scientific exchange, common dissemination, support in organizing events of mutual interest and coordination of input to standardization activities.

The current list of ongoing projects with which collaborations is being established is given below:

- B-WaterSmart - Water-smart economies and societies
- ULTIMATE: indUstry water-utiLiTy symbiosis for a sMarter wATer society
- WATER MINING Next generation water-smart management systems: large scale demonstrations for a circular economy and society
- REWAISE RESilient Water Innovation for Smart Economy

Those four projects are funded under the same call as WIDER UPTAKE, and from the very beginning the five coordinators have actively collaborated by starting a process of systematically mapping commonalities in terms of topics, case studies, technologies, methodological frameworks, target regions, and stakeholders. This has led to the creation of the network CIRSEAU. A regular exchange (every three months) between coordinators takes place. Between the CIRSEAU projects, there are now different cross-cutting working groups (WG) on which ideas are exchanged and efforts between the projects are leveraged and aligned. The WGs are:

- WG Communication and Dissemination (Lead IWW from B-WaterSmart)

- WG Assessment Frameworks (Lead Aqualia from REWISE)
- WG Stakeholder Engagement (Lead KWR from ULTIMATE)
- WG Young Water Professionals (Lead SINTEF from WIDER UPTAKE)
- WG Policy & Long-term Impact (Lead TU Delft from WATER MINING)

There are exchanges and joint event activities between the Young Water Professional Groups of the individual projects. Furthermore, the CIRSEAU projects submitted a joint workshop proposal to the IWA WWCE 2022, which was not accepted (possibly due to the world-wide focus of the conference, while the proposal may have been perceived as mainly EU oriented). However, the WG Communication and Dissemination continue to seek venues for joint participation.

Additionally, the opportunities of building from the findings of the following past H2020 projects will be investigated:

- FIWARE for the Next Generation Internet Services for the WATER sector: in relation to interoperability and data models.
- NextGen Towards a next generation of water systems and economy services for the circular economy: in relation to CE results and the marketplace for exploitation purposes.

Besides the WG meetings, the co-ordinators of the CIRSEAU projects meet each other and the POs from REA on a quarterly basis. To further promote CIRSEAU and facilitate long-term impacts a CIRSEAU presentation (Figure 24) has been prepared and a joint CSA application, CIRSEAU' was prepared and submitted to the call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-CIRC BIO-01 (Figure 25). The proposal was coordinated by the industry partner Aqualia in REWISE.

Figure 24 Example slides from the CIRSEAU presentation

Figure 25 Copy of front page of CIRSEAU application

4.4.9 Media relations

City and national media contact points (through the Partners and CIRSEAU working group on dissemination and communication) have been mapped by the partners to undertake

soft sounding¹ and other communication techniques to maximise the service positioning. See for instance the examples provided in Figure 10 and Figure 13.

4.4.10 EC channels and tools

Any relevant opportunity to communicate and disseminate the project activities and results via the EC and Horizon 2020 communication channels, including social media, will be considered to help raise the profile of the project and reach out to a wider audience. The WIDER UPTAKE Coordinator has established and will maintain regular communication with the Project Officer and inform about interesting news, results, and events.

In addition, we will consider using some of the free tools made available by the European Commission to H2020 projects, such as presented in Table 5, e.g., by sharing the success stories by the end of the project.

Table 5: Tools made available by the European Commission to H2020 projects

Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Magazine • Project stories • research*eu results magazine • Newsletters
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events on the CORDIS website

4.4.11 Policy brief and recommendations

In months 24 (D7.7) the project partner SINTEF has issued the first policy brief, Policy brief #1: [BROADENING THE SCOPE IN WATER MANAGEMENT](#). At M44 (D7.9), a second brief for policy developments based on the findings in the cases studies will be released. Refer also to section 0.

WP6 supports the dissemination of these recommendations by publication on the WIDER UPTAKE website and sharing in social media. All the partners will also support the dissemination of the recommendations by distributing them during EU or national policy events.

5 Open access and data management

As mentioned in section 4.4.5, a very important aspect is to guarantee the open access of the achieved results and data management. Indeed, all projects receiving Horizon 2020 funding are required to make sure that any peer-reviewed journal article they publish is openly accessible, free of charge (article 29.2. Model Grant Agreement). Specific measures to provide open access, including for instance the Gold open access, will be carried out by using a portion of the budget to each partner in WP6 for open access publication. Moreover, the Green open access (or self-archiving) will be implemented, by imposing that the final published paper or the final revised manuscript will be archived by the researcher in an online repository, before, alongside or after its publication.

¹ By “soft-sounding” we refer to contacts with journalists (which take place prior to e.g., the publication of a specific press release) to gauge their interest in the project or an issue.

WIDER UPTAKE makes use of the service provided by OpenAire and of the Zenodo repository² as the main tools to make our research data findable in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Mandate (see also section 4.4.5). A WIDER UPTAKE community has been established in the Zenodo repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community once they are approved by the EU Commission. Additional information regarding FAIR data management and Open Access for results from WIDER UPTAKE is included in D7.2 Data management plan_draft.

The Data Management Plan includes instruction regarding data sharing and accessibility in Open Access. Moreover, a description of the procedures to be adopted for the preservation of data in the short and long term is provided there.

6 Involvement of potential end-users and stakeholders in WIDER UPTAKE

The WIDER UPTAKE project cases studies are characterized by symbiotic relations between utilities and industries. There are in addition other stakeholders (e.g., public agencies, user groups) that together with the project partners are crucial for the exploitation of the innovations. The close connection between project partners and stakeholders involved in the cases is of huge importance for the developing the project roadmap that will aid in achieving improvement of the market uptake.

The engagement of stakeholders and end-users (industries, professionals, public administration, academic, etc.) is beneficial not only for achieving success in the project, but to stakeholders themselves. Interconnections have been established by sharing industrial, marketing, and commercial protocols according to the novel vision of “circular economy” market in the wastewater sector towards wider uptake of water-smart solutions.

The active use of the CoP that have been established in the project, at local level, project level and trans-project, are and have been instrumental to promote this involvement.

An example of a success story in which the solutions have been developed further through close collaboration with local stakeholders, is the progress towards implementation of wastewater reuse for agriculture in the Italian case. Also, in the Norwegian case, the market or business plan for recovered phosphorus has developed from the initial plan where the technology provider was obliged to buy the recovered struvite towards identifying a local, Norwegian market. The same can be said also for the Czech case but for wastewater reuse. However, the deciding issue remains in the National legislation. In Ghana the solutions both for wastewater reuse for agriculture and biochar to substitute wood-based charcoal are examples of successful exploitation results towards the creation of new companies/industrial activity focused on the CE and smart cities concept.

The involvement of stakeholders in the different local CoPs depend to an extent on the maturity of the solutions, but has increased compared to M18, with the mobile lab organised in Sicily as a good example, and the planned policy dialogue in Accra being another.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/wider-uptake/?page=1&size=20>

7 Barriers to the implementation of results from WIDER UPTAKE

Several barriers exist during the creation of innovative circular economy solutions involving water utilities and private businesses from industry sectors. These barriers represent the obstacles that the project aims to overcome. Among these barriers the most relevant are:

- Regulatory and institutional barriers which prevent the wide application of developed innovative solutions.
- Skills shortages within the wastewater treatment plants according to the circular economy concept.
- Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate.
- Mismatch between market needs and the solution.

During the WIDER UPTAKE project, focus on identifying and overcoming the barriers is faced and addressed by multiple WPs. In WP2, barriers related to compliance with quality and regulatory standards as well as health risks have been addressed. The risk assessment methodology is being implemented in the database, which will be a part of the final outcome of WIDER UPTAKE - the WIDER UPTAKE Roadmap Guide, which will be disseminated via the Water Europe Market Place. In WP3, the methodology for assessment of circularity and resource efficiency was delivered previously, and efforts in the second period has been on testing and verification of the methodology in the different demonstration cases. WP4, has previously delivered the basis for assessing the governance contexts and institutional networks, and will in M36 deliver the analysis of business models and strategies for industrial symbiosis based on water-smart solutions. WP5, has developed a methodology for assessing the water smartness and sustainability of symbiotic circular economy solutions that integrates inputs from the more detailed assessments in WPs 2-4 with inputs from the stakeholders on sustainability and weighting by local decisionmakers.

These tools will find their final form in RP3 and be included in the roadmap guide. It is though it's application a direct contribution can be provided to overcome barriers against implementation. To guide this development, stakeholders from the private sector and public administration will be involved in testing the roadmap guide as supporters for selecting the best actions to take in view of overcoming these barriers.

Developing countries may presents peculiar challenges in dissemination and exploitation of results that may be addressed by innovative approaches. WIDER UPTAKE benefits from the case in Ghana to employ a novel dissemination approach specifically suited for the context in a developing country. Critical actors will be prioritised to cover the entire chain of stakeholders required and in a set of dedicated events (seminars, workshops, demonstrations, field visits, participation in fairs and exhibitions, etc.). As noted above, a policy dialogue is planned in addition to being involved in the finalisation of the WIDER UPTAKE Roadmap Guide.

8 Implementation of results beyond project completion

The outcomes of WIDER UPTAKE and the knowledge created will continue to maximise their impact beyond the project end by making it available through a knowledge portal.

To this purpose, the original plan was to establish a Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre (VLSC) for Water-Smart Solutions as part of the project website and built as a community portal for networking and sharing data, tools, case studies and publications.

However, as mentioned in the DEP version 2, under the collaboration in CIRSEAU and as recommendation of the EC, emerged the opportunity to benefit for the same aim of the Knowledge Portal (Market Place) for solutions, information, training for water-smart CE solutions, has developed across multiple projects in the past H2020.

With the end of the [Nextgen](#) project in November 2022, the Market Place tool has been handed to Water Europe and is now available at the link <https://mp.watereurope.eu/>.

The Market Place is now managed by Water Europe in collaboration with NTUA (the technical University of Athens) and receives additional contributions by some of the CIRSEAU projects, such as B-WaterSmart and ULTIMATE, for its further improvement. The Market Place intends to offer to problem owners and solutions providers a visibility and matchmaking window between the demand and offer of innovative solutions. It is a versatile platform for networking, business development, discovering and sharing knowledge, and exhibiting achievement in the areas of Water, Energy, and Materials.

The Market Place, beyond hosting technical solutions, includes the case studies of the Nextgen project and welcomes the case studies of the CIRSEAU Projects in the [dedicated section](#) of the MP, that already hosts the cases of the ULTIMATE and B-WaterSmart. To this end, all CIRSEAU projects have been invited to upload their respective case studies through a dedicated application form online. WIDER UPTAKE will pursue this opportunity which has the benefit to ensure sustainability beyond the project since the knowledge portal will be permanently operated by Water Europe after the project.

The instructions to upload case studies with the respective circular technological synergies have been shared by Water Europe on 15th February 2023, including the description of the following steps and information to be considered for applications:

1. To upload the case studies a [representative of the project must first register in the MP <https://mp.watereurope.eu/registration/>](#)
2. After logging in, the form can be accessed by selecting “Case Studies” and then “Add a new case study” from the main menu, or by visiting the URL: <http://mp.watereurope.eu/admin/mp/casestudy/add/>.
3. Once the case study is uploaded, applicants can preview the factsheet, save their case study form for editing later or submit the form and apply for publication.
4. The CIRSEAU sister projects have been added to the project list for them to select.
5. Applicants can also create and store records for the organisations participating in the project.
6. After submission, Case Study Data Managers (Water Europe and NTUA) will review the applications, make necessary changes, or request amendments from the applicants and finally publish the factsheet(s) when all conditions are met.

The WIDER UPTAKE management team currently working on the coordination of inputs towards applying for the case studies upload in the Water Europe Market Place. It is expected to complete the application by July 2023.

Furthermore, another initiative and exploitation opportunity generated by the CIRSEAU network is the ongoing preparation of a joint proposal the Collaborative Research Action (CSA) as reported in section 4.4.8. The ambition, if the project is funded, is to build a

collaboration that generates strong synergies among the Circular Water Economy Community formed across EU projects and develop the CIRSEAU cluster as a self-sustained operational body to develop actions that strengthen European Green Deal and EU water-related policies, and the enhance market uptake, collaboration and knowledge sharing of water-smart symbiotic circular economy solutions.

9 Education and engagement of young professionals and researchers

A significant opportunity, in particular for the academic partners in WIDER UPTAKE, is to utilise all the dimensions in the project to promote the education of the next generation of stakeholders in the water sector and to prepare them for the transition into water smart solutions: young researchers and professionals and students at all levels: master, PhD's, and Post Doc. For young professionals at the industry partners and water utilities, the project gives insight into new possibilities for exploiting the value in water and inspiration for the future development of the water sector.

The high interdisciplinarity in the project and the possibility to compare similar technical solutions in different geographical, economic, and social contexts have an enormous educational value, to be taken advantage of.

WIDER UPTAKE has created an internal network among their PhD students and young practitioners called "Young Water Professionals". There are in total 20 young professionals registered in this sub-group of WIDER UPTAKE today. In addition to creating a stronger link across the academic institutions in the project, the young professionals have expressed the value of having such a multidisciplinary network among them.

A working group on Young Water Professionals has been established in CIRSEAU, where WIDER UPTAKE, ULTIMATE, B-WaterSmart and REWAISE (from October 2022) are active through YWP coordinators Karen Nessler Seglem, Raül Glotzbach, Kristina Wencki and Naiara Hernandez, respectively. Activities for the young professionals are from 2022 arranged across the projects through the YWP coordinators for each project. Through the projects we are able to give the young professionals the opportunity to practise networking amongst each other, and the possibility to learn directly from experts with long careers in the water sector, both on scientific and career topics:

- In January 2022, WIDER UPTAKE partners Hias (wastewater utility) and HiasHow2O (water treatment technology provider) held an expert presentation for the young professionals, including an online interactive session with Q&A and feedback on specific topics from the young professionals to the experts.
- In March 2022, an online event for the YWPs was held in connection with a B-WaterSmart consortium meeting. The event started with networking among the young professionals in smaller groups and was followed by a 'Hot-seat'-session with invited experts. Rita Ugarelli, Chief scientist at SINTEF, and Andrea Rubini, Director of operations at Water Europe sat in the 'hot-seat', where the young professionals could ask them anything, professional and private.

The YWP coordinators will continue to inform about activities in respective projects where the young water professionals could be invited across projects.

The YWP coordinators' general impression is that the young professionals are busy with scientific work within the projects, so participation in specific YWP events is difficult for

some of them. Therefore, from September 2022, the YWP coordinators have taken the initiative on a new type of activity to exploit the potential of having the voice of young water professionals available through the projects. As a result, two initiatives have been launched:

Initiative 1: Involvement of young water professionals in projects.

Targets:

- One-pager voicing ‘Why is it important to involve young water professionals in projects?’ Target audience: e.g., REA and other actors involved in the preparation of EU calls and tendering processes
- Workshop (e.g., attached to a fair event) arranged by the young water professionals to present and discuss the content of a one-pager and summary of success stories with the target audience

Initiative 2: Enthusing young water professionals in the water sector.

Targets:

- One-pager voicing young water professionals on their requests for attractive employers, appealing factors of the water sector and untapped potentials of an increased attractiveness and referring to success stories from companies/institutes. Target audience: e.g., HR managers and other decision makers in water companies
- Workshop (e.g., attached to a fair event) arranged by the young water professionals to present and discuss content of one-pager and summary of success stories with the target audience

An online information meeting with a presentation of these initiatives was held in November 2022. The meeting started with a networking session for the participants to keep working on this skill. Through the meeting, core groups to work on each of these initiatives was created. Further steps in this work are:

- April and May 2023: Specify one-pager content, format, and target. Define methodological approach for information collection for one-pager.
- December 2023: First draft of one-pager, type of event (format, target group) defined and discussed with CIRSEAU Communication and dissemination work group.
- May 2024 (latest): Event for the presentation and discussion of the one-pager should take place

YWP coordinator in B-WaterSmart, Kristina Wencki, has discussed opportunities for connecting YWP events to a Water Europe Event with Andrea Rubini and Isabella Gervasio in Water Europe. Three upcoming events have been identified:

- Water Knowledge Europe, in Oct/Nov 2023
- Water Market Europe, 2024 (no specific date yet)
- Water Projects Europe, 2024 (no specific date yet)

10 Monitoring and evaluation of activities

Continuous evaluation is necessary to analyse the effectiveness of the actions taken, to optimise future actions.

To facilitate monitoring and assessment, all partners are requested to:

- Prepare and update their individual action plans

- Conduct their dissemination and communication activities according to the global and individual action plans
- Keep the WP6 leader UNIPA updated about their dissemination activities as well as report on their activities during the update of the action plans (which actions were implemented, what supplementary activities were performed) and in the periodic reports to the EC.
- All partners should keep evidence of their implemented activities.

The following quantitative and qualitative KPIs have been defined to measure the effectiveness of the dissemination activities undertaken (Table 6).

wider uptake

Table 6: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE dissemination activities

Dissemination activity	Methodology	KPI	Target (End of the project)	Results Month 18	Results Month 36
<i>Project website</i>	Google analytics	Number of total visits	>30,000	Old webpage: 2020-2021: 3478	10226 (old+ new webpage)
<i>Social media /</i>	Twitter analytics LinkedIn Campaign Monitor	Interactions with Twitter and LinkedIn accounts.	600 followers 100 retweets 50 comments	431 followers on Twitter, 46 followers on LinkedIn	154 followers on LinkedIn, WiderUptake-UNIPA: 504 followers on LinkedIn, 496 on Twitter, 294 on Facebook
<i>Videos (Vimeo)</i>	Vimeo/YouTube analytics	No of animated videos published	1	1	1
		No of demo case videos published	5	4	8
<i>Media presence</i>	Dissemination reporting (Excel)	No of articles/press releases published	15		9
		No of articles/papers published	15	2	10
	Mentioned in Media		N.A.	66	
<i>Conferences & Events</i>	Dissemination reporting (Excel)	No of external events attended by WIDER UPTAKE partners	30	6	20
		No of events organized at demo sites	At least one communication event at each demonstration site during the lifetime of the project	3	7

wider uptake

D6.5 – Updated dissemination and exploitation plan M36

<i>Synergies & multiplier contacts</i>	<i>List of related initiatives/projects /multipliers identified and proof of contact</i>	No of synergies/contacts	10	1 (composed of 4 projects)	5 (i.e., 1 from M18; 2 Italian proposals; 1 Norwegian initiative; the CIRSEAU CSA)
<i>Newsletter</i>	No of newsletter published	No of newsletter published /month	1 every 6 months	2	3
<i>Workshops Including training activities and summer schools</i>	<i>Dissemination reporting (Excel)</i>	Number of workshops	3 workshops/year	6	19 (local CoP workshops)
<i>Policy briefs</i>	<i>Policy brief produced</i>	Number of policy briefs	2	None yet, planned for later in the project	1

Table 7: Summary of WIDER UPTAKE exploitation activities

Measure or activity	Methodology	KPI for the measure or activity	Target (End of the project)	Results Month 18	Results Month 36
Supporting companies in the further development of their business plans	<p>WIDER UPTAKE will set up and execute a plan for industrial network development, closely linked with the demonstration cases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o A triple-layered business model canvas for dialogue-based assessment and identification of specific symbiosis models for the demonstration cases will be applied. o Important aspects in an industrial symbiosis will be addressed in workshops for each demonstration case, coordinated with WP1. <p>For the case studies in the project this will be part of WP4 and WP1.</p>	No. of new/improved business plans for the participating industries	5	None yet, planned for later in the project	Results for 5 demonstration cases in D4.2
Improve symbiotic solutions	<p>WIDER UPTAKE will use the tools developed in the project to analyse the symbiotic solutions according to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Health and safety management tool o Optimisation of resource efficiency and value chains o Governance assessment o Holistic assessment of sustainability <p>For the case studies in the project this will be part of WP2-5 and WP1.</p>	Progress towards SDGs as measured by WP5 tool	N/A, based on the WP5 results	None yet, planned for later in the project	Results for 2 demonstration cases in D5.2.

wider uptake

D6.5 – Updated dissemination and exploitation plan M36

<p>Supporting the sharing of non-proprietary information</p>	<p>Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre making available the roadmap and all the knowledge acquired during the project</p>	<p>Number of registered users having actively accessed and used the portal by M36</p>	<p>30 organizations and 200 individuals</p>	<p>None yet, planned for later in the project</p>	<p>First version of the WU Roadmap Guide in D6.6</p>
<p>Stakeholder interaction</p>	<p>Sessions of collaborative work will be held with the Local (L) and Project (P) CoPs and synergies created within the Trans- project CoPs.</p> <p>Targets and reported numbers include both physical and virtual events.</p>	<p>L-CoP: No. of events</p> <p>P- CoP: No. of events</p> <p>Trans project CoP: number of connected communities</p>	<p>Local CoP: 15</p> <p>Project CoP: 12</p> <p>Trans project CoP: 3</p>	<p>L-CoP: 6</p> <p>P-CoP: 4</p> <p>Trans-CoP: 1 (CIRSEAU)</p>	<p>L-CoP: 19</p> <p>P-CoP: 8</p> <p>Trans-CoP: 1 (CIRSEAU)</p>

